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Some Stationary Sequences

In Florentin Smarandache: "Collected Papers", vol. II. Chisinau
(Moldova): Universitatea de Stat din Moldova, 1997.

[Published in "Gamma", Brasov, XXIII, Anul VIII, No. 1, October 1985, pp. 5-6.]

SOME STATIONARY SEQUENCES

§1. Define a sequence $\{a_n\}$ by $a_1 = a$ and $a_{n+1} = P(a_n)$, where P is a polynomial with real coefficients. For which a values, and for which P polynomials will this sequence be constant after a certain rank?

In this note, the author answers this question using as reference F. Lazebnik & Y. Pilipenko's E 3036 problem from A. M. M., Vol. 91, No. 2/1984, p. 140.

An interesting property of functions admitting fixed points is obtained.

§2. Because $\{a_n\}$ is constant after a certain rank, it results that $\{a_n\}$ converges. Hence, $(\exists)e \in \mathbb{R} : e = P(e)$, that is the equation $P(x) - x = 0$ admits real solutions. Or P admits fixed points $((\exists)x \in \mathbb{R} : P(x) = x)$.

Let e_1, \dots, e_m be all real solutions of this equation. It constructs the recurrent set E as follows:

- 1) $e_1, \dots, e_m \in E$;
- 2) if $b \in E$ then all real solutions of the equation $P(x) = b$ belong to E ;
- 3) no other element belongs to E , then the obtained elements from the rule 1) or 2), applying for a finite number of times these rules.

We prove that this set E , and the set A of the "a" values for which $\{a_n\}$ becomes constant after a certain rank are indistinct, " $E \subseteq A$ ".

- 1) If $a = e_i, 1 \leq i \leq m$, then $(\forall)n \in \mathbb{N}^* \quad a_n = e_i = \text{constant}$.
- 2) If for $a = b$ the sequence $a_1 = b, a_2 = P(b)$ becomes constant after a certain rank, let x_0 be a real solution of the equation $P(x) - b = 0$, the new formed sequence: $a'_1 = x_0, a'_2 = P(x_0) = b, a'_3 = P(b) \dots$ is indistinct after a certain rank with the first one, hence it becomes constant too, having the same limit.
- 3) Beginning from a certain rank, all these sequences converge towards the same limit e (that is: they have the same e value from a certain rank) are indistinct, equal to e .

" $A \subseteq E$ "

Let "a" be a value such that: $\{a_n\}$ becomes constant (after a certain rank) equal to e . Of course $e \in \{e_1, \dots, e_m\}$ because e_1, \dots, e_m are the single values towards these sequences can tend.

If $a \in \{e_1, \dots, e_m\}$, then $a \in E$.

Let $a \notin \{e_1, \dots, e_m\}$, then $(\exists)n_0 \in \mathbb{N} : a_{n_0+1} = P(a_{n_0}) = e$, hence we obtain applying the rules 1) or 2) a finite number of times. Therefore, because $e \in \{e_1, \dots, e_m\}$ and the equation $P(x) = e$ admits real solutions we find a_{n_0} among the real solutions of this equation: knowing a_{n_0} we find a_{n_0-1} because the equation $P(a_{n_0-1}) = a_{n_0}$ admits real solutions (because $a_{n_0} \in E$ and our method goes on until we find $a_1 = a$ hence $a \in E$).

Remark. For $P(x) = x^2 - 2$ we obtain the E 3036 Problem (A. M. M.).

Here, the set E becomes equal to

$$\{\pm 1, 0, \pm 2\} \cup \left\{ \underbrace{\pm \sqrt{2 \pm \sqrt{2 \pm \sqrt{\dots \pm 2}}}}_{n_0 \text{ times}}, n \in \mathbb{N}^* \right\} \cup \left\{ \underbrace{\pm \sqrt{2 \pm \sqrt{\dots \sqrt{2 \pm \sqrt{3}}}}}_{n_0 \text{ times}}, n \in \mathbb{N} \right\}.$$

Hence, for all $a \in E$ the sequence $a_1 = a$, $a_{n+1} = a_n^2 - 2$ becomes constant after a certain rank, and it converges (of course) towards -1 or 2 :

$$(\exists) n_0 \in \mathbb{N}^* : (\forall) n \geq n_0 \quad a_n = -1$$

or

$$(\exists) n_0 \in \mathbb{N}^* : (\forall) n \geq n_0 \quad a_n = 2.$$